

Composer: Mei-ling Lee

Composition: Summoner

Project Description:

Summoner, a music composition performance, is created using Kyma by Symbolic Sound Corporation, Max software by Cycling '74, and the Leap Motion Controller by Ultraleap. All performative movements are based on turning an intangible sound into an imaginary physical object.

Program Notes:

The elusive and mysterious owls, with their nocturnal nature, have been associated with magic, mysticism, and the occult. Though symbols of wisdom and fortune, their presence is often considered a harbinger of death and destruction.

Peafowl, on the other hand, are seen as symbols of divinity, royalty, and immortality, and manifestations of majesty and charisma. Their beauty and vibrant colors are praised as a gift from divine beings.

Summoner explores the mysteries associated with these two members of Class Aves. Using peafowl recordings made at my mother-in-law's home, where more than two dozen peafowl reside, this composition transforms the sounds of peacocks calling and owls hooting, and takes an excursion into the enigmas, mythologies, and necromancy of these creatures.